

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING ACTIVITY ON THE BASIS OF COGNITIVE-MOTIVATIONAL APPROACH - THE REQUIREMENT OF THE CURRENT DAY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506395>

Abstract. *This article covers theoretical and practical issues related to the methodology for developing students' independent learning activities on the basis of a cognitive-motivational approach. The ideas and opinions of foreign and national researchers on the implementation of students' independent learning are presented. In this regard, the researchers substantiate the need to take into account the influence of the social environment in society, pedagogical-psychological and technological factors on students' independent learning.*

The role of modern technologies in organizing the independent learning process is highlighted, and the effectiveness of using online educational platforms and electronic resources is shown. At the end of the article, the need to further deepen scientific research on the integration of national culture and traditions into the educational process in organizing the process of cognitive and motivational approach in a person-oriented manner is emphasized, as well as the need to develop new methods and technologies in this process and apply them in practice. For example, it is noted that the introduction of special courses on national history, art and traditions into the educational process is an important step in developing students' national consciousness, and it is important to encourage research in this area and introduce them into the education system.

Keywords: *cognitive approach, motivational approach, independent learning, interactive method, integration, method, online educational platforms, motivational approach, national culture, national value.*

INTRODUCTION. One of the priorities of the reforms being carried out in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the higher education sector is to direct future specialists to self-improvement, develop the ability to independently acquire knowledge, and prepare them for the effective use of innovative processes. To fulfill such a task, it is not enough to be limited to the information provided by the teacher. Therefore, recently, special emphasis has been placed on increasing the student potential to acquire independent knowledge through organizing their independent activities.

Training specialists with the ability to think independently and creatively in the educational process is of great importance. One of the important issues is the involvement of young people in the educational process, increasing their talents and level of knowledge, and teaching them professional disciplines and organizing their independent creative activities properly. Our society needs specialists who think deeply in various fields and can make decisions of their own. Teaching students to think independently remains one of the main tasks in the process of education and upbringing.

The ability to think independently is important throughout a student's life and at each stage of education. Thinking or reasoning is a high manifestation of a student's mental process,

perception, conscious behavior and intelligence. The term "independent education" is explained in pedagogical dictionaries as an educational process achieved outside educational institutions, through personal independent research. Also, the concepts of "independent learning", "self-improvement" and "independent learning process" are used as synonyms. [1]

Relevance of the topic. In today's rapidly evolving era, characterized by advancing technologies, globalization, and digitalization in education, the demand for independent learning is growing. Modern education aims to shape students not merely as recipients of information but as individuals who actively seek and process knowledge and apply innovative approaches in practice. [2]

The cognitive and motivational approaches have particular significance in the educational process. These methods effectively enhance students' intellectual potential, spark their interest in learning, and guide them toward self-education. In an innovation-driven economy, there is a pressing need for individuals who can think creatively and independently and who are adept at acquiring new knowledge.

In our country, large-scale reforms to improve the education system place great emphasis on fostering independent learning. This focus is critical for equipping young people with the modern skills and expertise necessary to excel in their chosen professions and transform into competitive specialists.

From this perspective, fostering independent educational activities based on cognitive and motivational approaches has become a pressing need. This topic is not only a vital area of scientific research but also a cornerstone of practical education. Such approaches will play a pivotal role in the future by enhancing the cognitive potential of youth, cultivating innovative thinking skills, and preparing a workforce capable of driving societal development.

A brief analysis of scientific sources on the topic

The topic of developing students' independent learning activities based on cognitive-motivational approaches is widely studied in both global and national pedagogical research. Scientific sources in this field encompass theoretical and practical approaches to ensuring an integrative perspective in the learning process and enhancing students' intellectual and motivational potential. The following points highlight these aspects:

Sources on Cognitive Approaches

Research in cognitive psychology and educational theory gives information about the works of such scholars as J. Piaget, L. Vygotsky, and J. Bruner. Their studies focus on the stages of cognitive development and the characteristics of how students receive, process, and assimilate information during the learning process. L. Vygotsky's theory of the "zone of proximal development" is particularly notable for its application in developing students' intellectual abilities. His ideas provide a theoretical foundation for progressively mastering complex tasks in independent learning. [3]

Theories of Motivation

Motivation plays an important role in enhancing students' interest and engagement in the learning process. Theories such as A. Maslow's hierarchy of needs, D. McClelland's "need for achievement" theory, and the intrinsic motivation concept by E. Deci and R. Ryan offer valuable strategies for increasing students' interest in education. Among national researchers, N. Yodgorov and A. Jurayev have studied the social, spiritual, and personal factors of motivation. Their works emphasize the importance of balancing intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in student activities.

Methods for Developing Independent Learning

In Europe, the Bologna Process has emphasized independent learning, focusing on organizing self-study tasks and utilizing technical tools and electronic resources.

Among Uzbek researchers, Professor U. Abdullayev has studied the role of information technologies in developing independent learning and it deserves special attention. His research highlights the importance of online learning platforms and improving students' information literacy.

Additionally, the works of scholars such as A. Khaydarov and M. Sharipov underscore the significance of using creative assignments, group projects, and interactive teaching methods to facilitate students' independent activities.

Modern sources. In modern research, the role of artificial intelligence and virtual learning platforms in developing students' cognitive and motivational characteristics is widely studied. For example, platforms such as Coursera, Edx and Moodle prove to be effective in developing students' independent learning activities in the educational process. [4]

Main part. The formation and development of independent learning activities of students in the current modern education system is one of the urgent tasks. Scientific and technological progress, the development of information technologies and the requirements for human intellectual potential require the reorganization of the educational process on the basis of innovative approaches. In this case, cognitive and motivational approaches play an important role in the effective organization of independent learning activities of students. This article considers theoretical and practical issues related to the methodology for developing independent learning activities of students based on the cognitive-motivational approach.

Independent learning is the organization of the learning process, aimed at the personal and professional development of students, using their own strengths and resources. In this process, students are the main subjects of learning, that is, they manage their own learning process through active actions. The effective development of independent learning is one of the main tasks of modern education, which serves to form students' ability to think independently, solve problems independently, and increase their creative potential.

Students' independent learning process depends on many factors. They can be divided into the following categories:

1. Social factors: the attitude of society towards the student period, the social significance of education, and the relationships of students with their parents, teachers, and peers affect independent learning.

2. Psychological factors: the personal characteristics of students, including their level of motivation, abilities, interest in learning, and similar characteristics determine their level of independence.

3. Pedagogical factors: the organization of the educational process, the effectiveness of pedagogical methods and tools affect students' independent learning activities.

4. Technological factors: the availability of information and communication technologies, online learning platforms, and electronic textbooks help support students' independent learning processes.

Methodological features based on a cognitive-motivational approach. The following methodological principles are taken as the basis for developing students' independent learning activities based on a cognitive-motivational approach:

Individual approach: taking into account the individual characteristics of each student and selecting appropriate educational materials for them. For example, complex materials may be presented for students with higher cognitive abilities, while simpler materials may be presented for others.

Motivational stimulation: organizing the learning process taking into account the interests of students, providing social and personal incentives.

Interdisciplinary approach: deepening students' knowledge and developing independent thinking by establishing connections between different disciplines.

Using interactive methods: ensuring active participation of students through group work, debates, case studies, analysis and reflection processes.

Using information technologies: expanding opportunities for independent learning through electronic textbooks, online courses, simulations and virtual laboratories.

Assessment and monitoring of the independent learning process. The following indicators can be used to assess the effectiveness of the independent learning process:

- the pace and quality of students' knowledge acquisition;
- the quality level of independent work performed;
- the growth of interest and motivation in the independent learning process;
- the accuracy and effectiveness of the results achieved by them. [5]

We can advise to widely use the reflection method in the assessment process. Students will have the opportunity to analyze their strengths and weaknesses and plan their future activities. At the same time, students' interest can be increased by providing regular feedback from teachers and recognizing their personal successes.

The cognitive-motivational approach is a very effective methodological basis for developing students' independent learning activities. This approach serves to increase students' interest in the learning process, enhance their intellectual potential, and develop their creative abilities. In the modern education system, the development of new pedagogical technologies that ensure the personal development of students by integrating cognitive and motivational approaches is of great importance.

During independent learning process, it is important to study national culture and traditions and integrate them into the educational process. Today's requirements, even in the era of globalization and rapid development of technologies, require the preservation of national values and the enrichment of the process of learning based on them. This approach is especially important in the formation of students as qualified specialists with the ability to think creatively and independently.

Determining the importance of national values in the educational process is one of the main directions of today's pedagogical research. National culture is one of the main factors influencing the human mind, through which it is possible to strengthen the spiritual and educational impact in the educational process. The introduction of national culture into the educational process stimulates not only the ability of students to learn, but also their personal development. For example, through educational programs based on national traditions, students develop a need for self-development. [6]

The combination of national values with modern information technologies in the educational process is of particular importance. The presence of resources related to national culture on online educational platforms can interest students in the independent learning process

and increase their motivation to learn. The educational value of national culture is manifested not only in the acquisition of modern knowledge, but also in its enrichment with national consciousness and culture.

Also, the development of creative activity in the process of independent learning is of great importance in realizing the personal abilities of students. It is possible to develop students' creative abilities based on information from national traditions, for example, folk crafts, music or literature. The educational process, organized on the basis of a creative approach, increases not only students' knowledge, but also their ability to create new ideas.

The task of educators should not be limited only to imparting knowledge, but also to supporting students in achieving independence. Teachers contribute to the formation of the younger generation as a well-rounded individual by explaining to students the importance of national values in the educational process, involving them in scientific and creative activities.

It is necessary to further deepen scientific research on the integration of national culture and traditions into the educational process. In this process, it is necessary to develop new methods and technologies and apply them in practice. For example, the introduction of special courses on national history, art and traditions into the educational process can be an important step in developing students' national consciousness. It is also important to encourage research in this area and introduce them into the education system.

Educational programs organized on the basis of national values help to understand national identity. This approach encourages young people not only to personal development, but also to preserve the spiritual and cultural wealth of society. One of the most effective ways to preserve and develop national culture is to convey it to the younger generation in the educational process.

In conclusion, the integration of national culture and traditions into the educational process is an important condition for developing students' creative and independent learning abilities. Through this approach, it is possible to prepare the younger generation as a comprehensively developed individual and ensure their place in modern society. Therefore, national values should be an integral part of the educational process.

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